

A heuristic alternative to dark energy

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Abstract

The nature of dark energy, which is presumed to accelerate the expansion of the Universe, has remained a mystery for three decades. A heuristic hypothesis is explored here which ascribes the observed acceleration to a non-uniformity of the time coordinate of the expansion (t') with respect to the cosmic time (t) which is based on physical interactions. Assuming a power law relating t' to t with the exponent as the only free parameter, the proposed time-inhomogeneity plus cold dark matter (TCDM) model fits well recent cosmological datasets on the cosmic microwave background (CMB), baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) and Type Ia supernovae (SNeIa). The best TCDM fit to all datasets combined is obtained with the exponent $b_t = 2.092 \pm 0.015$ and the present matter density $\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1416 \pm 0.0012$ without requiring dark energy. It is a significantly better fit than the best-fit Λ CDM model which yields the same $\Omega_m h^2$ and the Hubble-Lemaître parameter $H_0 = 68.01 \pm 0.65 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. Prospects for discriminating between the models with forthcoming data are discussed.

1 Introduction

The Universe is expanding nearly twice as fast as predicted by the density of matter that it contains, comprising both baryonic and dark matter. The Hubble-Lemaître parameter (H_0) which is the present rate of expansion, has been measured to be in the range of $67 - 73 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. The nearly 5σ difference between the value inferred from the cosmic microwave background (CMB) and direct measurements is referred to as the “Hubble tension” (see L. Verde et al. 2024 for a review). The density of matter, however, which is measured precisely with CMB data, implies $H_0 \simeq 38 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ for a flat universe. Furthermore, measurements of distant Type Ia supernovae (SNeIa) revealed that the expansion is accelerating (S. Perlmutter et al. 1999, A. G. Riess et al. 1998). These deviations from a matter-driven expansion have been attributed to an entity named dark energy constituting $\sim 70\%$ of the energy density of the Universe at present (M. S.

Turner & M. White 1997). Mathematically, its simplest description is given by Einstein’s cosmological constant Λ . In the Friedmann equation Λ adds an energy density which remains constant throughout the expansion of the Universe, becoming dominant over matter whose density decreases as $a(t)^{-3}$, where $a(t)$ is the scale factor. The combination of dark energy and cold dark matter (CDM) has led to the concordance model (Λ CDM) of cosmology.

Extensive research in the last decades has failed to identify the physical nature of dark energy. Quantum vacuum energy would be a natural candidate, however it is over 120 orders of magnitude too big. Other hypotheses include new scalar fields, “quintessence” and modified gravity. For a comprehensive review see L. Amendola & S. Tsujikawa 2010 and E. Di Valentino et al. 2021. It should be noted that the nature of dark matter has also not been identified so far. However, its presence can be detected and quantified by using gravitational lensing and other effects. In contrast, dark energy remains elusive and a determi-

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nation of its equation of state in the Λ CDM model, $w = -P/\rho = -1$ (where P is the pressure and ρ is the density), requires a precision measurement of the expansion history of the Universe. Several projects are under way or are planned to achieve this difficult goal, including the Dark Energy Survey (DES), the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI), the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF), the Square Kilometer Array (SKA), as well as the space telescopes Euclid and Roman. Extensions of the basic dark energy model, with $w \neq -1$ (w CDM model) or a time-dependent w (w_0w_a CDM model) have also been considered and used to fit cosmological data.

In this paper a heuristic alternative to dark energy is proposed, motivated by the symmetry of cosmological space and time. The key assumption is that the Universe, containing only matter and radiation, expands with a time coordinate (t') which is different from the customary cosmic time (t) and varies non-uniformly with respect to it. t is the time coordinate in the FLRW metric and is generally linked to physical processes which can serve as clocks (S.E. Rugh & H. Zinkernagel 2009). It is replaced by t' in this paper, which is not linked to physical processes other than the expansion. An increasing dt'/dt with t will cause the matter-driven expansion to appear accelerated when analysed in terms of t . Just as the space coordinates of the Universe expand as $a(t)$ with respect to physical dimensions such as the average size of a galaxy, the time coordinate t' accelerates with respect to t . The dimensions of objects, such as atoms or galaxies, whose size is determined by physical interactions, are not affected by the spatial expansion $a(t)$. Similarly, the cosmic time t , as determined from physical interactions, such as atomic transitions, is assumed to be unaffected by the acceleration of t' .

t' will be referred to as cosmological time in this paper. t is the customary cosmic time,¹ however, to avoid confusion, it will be referred to as physical time as it is measured using specific physical processes. It is generally assumed to be uniform since the Big Bang, to the extent that the coupling constants of physical interactions do not vary. Indeed, measurements of the redshift (z) of distant galaxies using atomic emission lines are based on

¹A few authors use the term cosmological time instead of cosmic time, however, it is clear from the context that they refer to cosmic time.

the assumption that the line frequency was the same in the rest frame of the emitter several billion years ago as it is now on Earth. Physical time is slowed down, however, by the gravitational field (e.g. L. B. Okun et al. 1999) as observed with satellite-born atomic clocks and the Shapiro effect (I. I. Shapiro 1964).

The time-inhomogeneity hypothesis, which also includes cold dark matter, will be referred to as the TCDM model hereafter. Assuming a power law dependence of t' on t , with the initial condition $dt'/dt = 1$ at the Big Bang, TCDM can fit recent cosmological data on the CMB, on SNeIa (DES & Pantheon+ compilation) and from DESI on baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) as well as or better than the Λ CDM model. Fitting all datasets combined, TCDM is significantly better than Λ CDM without requiring dark energy.

A time-inhomogeneity which is conceptually similar to the time-acceleration of TCDM has been derived through a special conformal transformation (L. M. Tomilchik 2014 and references therein) and will be discussed in the next section.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 the TCDM model is presented. In Section 3 it is confronted to several datasets and compared with Λ CDM. The conclusions and future tests of the model are discussed in Section 4.

2 The TCDM model

2.1 Model outline

A flat universe will be assumed throughout this paper, which is consistent with Planck CMB data (Planck collaboration 2020, hereafter Planck). The model can be extended to non-zero curvature.

In the TCDM model the expansion of the Universe is due to radiation and matter only, with a scale factor $a'(t')$ which obeys the Friedmann equation expressed in terms of t' in the FLRW metric:

$$\left[\frac{da'(t')}{a'(t') dt'} \right]^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \left[\frac{\rho_r}{a'(t')^4} + \frac{\rho_m}{a'(t')^3} \right] \quad (1)$$

where G is Newton's gravitational constant, ρ_r is the present radiation density, which is determined by the blackbody (CMB) temperature, and ρ_m is the present matter density including both baryonic and dark matter.

ρ_m is determined precisely by CMB data (Planck) in terms of the parameter combination

Figure 1: (a) *Upper panel*: The time interval $\Delta t'$ and Δt to expand by an increment $\Delta a = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ in the EdS (dotted line) and the Λ CDM (dashed line) models respectively as a function of redshift. The corresponding best-fit TCDM model (solid line) nearly overlaps Λ CDM. (b) *Lower panel*: The ratio of $\Delta t'$ and Δt curves in (a) as a function of the Λ CDM lookback time (dashed line). The derivative of $b(t)$ which defines the TCDM time t'' is shown by the solid line.

$\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1430 \pm 0.0011$ (0.8% precision):

$$\rho_m = \frac{3\bar{H}_0^2 \Omega_m h^2}{8\pi G} = (2.686 \pm 0.021) 10^{-27} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \quad (2)$$

where Ω_m is the ratio of the present matter density to the critical density (ρ_c) implied by the H_0 measurement, $\bar{H}_0 = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and h is the reduced Hubble-Lemaître parameter, $h = H_0/\bar{H}_0$. This model will be referred to as the Einstein-de Sitter (EdS) universe (A. Einstein & W. De Sitter 1932) with radiation added and its parameters indicated by primes.

In the EdS universe H'_0 is determined essentially by the present matter density, $H'_0 = 37.8 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ using $\Omega_m h^2$ from Planck. This im-

plies an age of $t'_0 = 2/(3H'_0) = 17.2 \text{ Gyr}$ (EdS time) which corresponds to $t_0 \sim 13.8 \text{ Gyr}$ in physical time (Λ CDM), which in turn determines the age of the oldest stars.

The key assumption of the TCDM model is that the cosmological time coordinate t' of EdS differs from the physical time t . It is assumed that initially $dt'/dt = 1$ and that it is increasing with t since then. This results in a different time dependence of the scale factor $a(t)$ when analyzed in terms of t . This is illustrated in Figure 1(a) where the time intervals $\Delta t'$ and Δt to expand by the same increment Δa are plotted as a function of redshift for the EdS and Λ CDM² models of same matter density, respectively. The Λ CDM model is the reference for the best-fit TCDM model (which is presented in Section 3.2) with $H_0 = 67.77 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_m = 0.3082$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 1 - \Omega_m$.

Using the same increment Δa for the EdS and Λ CDM models results in a common z . In Figure 1(a) $\Delta t'$ (EdS) increases as z decreases, as expected for slowing expansion, while Δt (Λ CDM) decreases for $z < 1$, corresponding to an acceleration which is ascribed to dark energy.

In Figure 1(b) the ratio of the $\Delta t'$ and Δt curves of Figure 1(a) is plotted as a function of the lookback time of the reference Λ CDM model. The ratio is well approximated by a power law:

$$dt'/dt = [1 + b_0(t/t_0)^{b_t}] = db(t)/dt \quad (3)$$

where t_0 is the age of the Universe in the reference Λ CDM model. The initial condition $dt'/dt = 1$ is satisfied for $t = t' = 0$ at the Big Bang. This power law is used as an ansatz to transform the cosmological time t' to the TCDM time t'' which is to be compared with the physical time t . The constant b_0 is determined by the ratio of the expansion rates H_0 and H'_0 , at present:

$$dt'/dt = 1 + b_0 = (\Omega_m + \Omega_r)^{-1/2} \quad (4)$$

where $\Omega_r = \rho_r/\rho_c$, Ω_m and H_0 specify the reference Λ CDM model. This definition of b_0 ensures that $\Delta t'' = \Delta t$ at present, so that results are compared using the same time scale. The cosmological time scale $\Delta t'$ at present, however, is a factor ~ 1.8 greater than the physical (cosmic) time scale Δt . The very small difference between the TCDM and

² Λ CDM calculated by numerical integration agrees exactly with Astropy `LambdaCDM` with $T=2.7255^\circ \text{ K}$ for the CMB temperature and $N_{eff} = 3.04$ for the radiation density.

Λ CDM models during past expansion, as can be seen in Figure 1, is significant in fitting the cosmological data in Section 3.

The integral of Equation (3) gives t' , the elapsed time since the Big Bang, in terms of t :

$$t' = b(t) = t \left[1 + \frac{b_0}{(1 + b_t)} \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right)^{b_t} \right] \quad (5)$$

The elapsed time t'' of the TCDM model is a transformation of the EdS time t' by the same factor to compare to the elapsed physical time:

$$t'' = t' \left[1 + \frac{b_0}{(1 + b_t)} \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right)^{b_t} \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

This time transformation maps the scale factor, $a(x)$, from EdS time ($x = t'$) to TCDM time ($x = t''$). In other words, the array $a_i(x)$ has the same value for the three models, with $x = t_i, t'_i$ integrated numerically from the Friedmann equation for Λ CDM and EdS models respectively and $x = t''_i$ given by Equation (6).

As noted above, TCDM is defined relative to a reference Λ CDM model which represents the physical (cosmic) time scale. Since Λ CDM parameters are not unique but depend on the dataset that is fit, TCDM is also calculated separately for each Λ CDM model. While Ω_m and H_0 specify the Λ CDM model, ρ_m (i.e. $\Omega_m h^2$) and the exponent b_t specify the corresponding TCDM model. The cosmological quantities of TCDM are indicated by double primes and are calculated as shown below.

2.2 SNIa distance

The cosmological distances are calculated in the TCDM model in the usual way, using the time coordinate t'' instead of t . The comoving distance D''_C to an object emitting at time t''_e is given by:

$$D''_C(t''_e) = \int_{t''_e}^{t''_0} \frac{c dt''}{a''(t'')} \quad (7)$$

where t''_0 is the age of the Universe in the TCDM model. The distance modulus, μ , is given by:

$$\mu''(z) = 5 \log[(1 + z)D''_C(z)/10\text{pc}] \quad (8)$$

where $z = (1/a''(t''_e) - 1)$ is common to all three models.

2.3 Big-bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN)

In the first minutes of the Universe when the expansion is driven by radiation, the time coordinates t, t' and t'' are identical. Therefore, the BBN parameters calculated using the physical time of the Λ CDM model also apply to the EdS and TCDM models. An important parameter is the present baryon density $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02190 \pm 0.00025$ which has been calculated to 1.1% precision subject to the constraints of primordial ^4He mass fraction (Y_P) and the deuterium abundance (D/H) (C. Pitrou et al. 2018).

This precision BBN analysis has been used to set a limit on the variation of the gravitational constant G at the BBN epoch from its present value G_0 : $G/G_0 = 0.98 \pm 0.06$ (1σ) (J. Alvey et al. 2020). Since $H_0 \propto \sqrt{G}$, this limit is equivalent to a 95% confidence interval of 0.93 – 1.05 for the fractional variation of H_0 due to a time dependence of G . The range of this variation is comparable to the Hubble tension, however a more detailed analysis is required to check their consistency. A limit on the variation of the physical (cosmic) time scale in the BBN epoch from its present value could also be set, with the free neutron decay lifetime of 879.5 ± 0.8 s (as used in the BBN analysis above) providing a significant constraint.

2.4 CMB

Up to the time of the last scattering of CMB photons at $z_* = 1090$ ($t_* \sim 0.37$ Myr), the expansion is driven by radiation and matter and is identical for the EdS, TCDM and Λ CDM models for the same matter density. The comoving sound horizon (r_*) is calculated following K. Cahill 2020:

$$r_* = \int_0^{t_*} \frac{c dt}{a(t) \sqrt{3(1 + R)}} \quad (9)$$

where $R = 3a(t)\Omega_b h^2 / 4\Omega_\gamma h^2$. The CMB determination of $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02237 \pm 0.00015$ (Planck) is 2% higher than the BBN value above and will be used in this paper for consistency, unless indicated otherwise. The present photon density $\Omega_\gamma h^2 = 2.4730 \times 10^{-5}$ is determined by the CMB temperature $T = 2.7255^\circ$ K. These yield $r_* = 144.71$ Mpc (144.75 Mpc) for the best-fit Λ CDM (TCDM) model presented in Section 3.2.

The angle (θ_*) of the acoustic peak of the CMB power spectrum is then given by (neglecting the

very small lensing correction):

$$\theta_* = \frac{r_*}{D_C(z_*)} \quad \text{where} \quad D_C(z_*) = \int_{t_*}^{t_0} \frac{c dt}{a(t)} \quad (10)$$

is the comoving radial distance travelled by a CMB photon since t_* in the Λ CDM model. The corresponding distance $D_C''(z_*)$ in the TCDM model is calculated similarly, using t'' and $a''(t'')$. The model dependence in θ_* is essentially through $D_C(z_*)$ which allows to determine H_0 indirectly from CMB data (L. Knox & M. Millea 2020).

θ_* is measured with 0.03% precision (Planck) nearly independently of models. It is a strong constraint and is used in all the fits (except one) of the TCDM model, as described below. Fitting the full CMB power spectrum is beyond the scope of this paper.

2.5 BAO

The baryon acoustic oscillation parameters are based on the comoving sound horizon (r_d) at the end of the drag epoch, $z_d = 1060$. It is calculated as in Equation (9) and has the value of 147.41 Mpc for the best-fit TCDM model and its EdS and Λ CDM counterparts. It is used as a standard ruler to determine the following distances in the terminology of the DESI Collaboration 2025a (hereafter DESI2):

- $D_M(z)$ is the transverse comoving distance which is identical to $D_C(z)$ for a flat universe. It is measured from the angle subtended by r_d perpendicular to the line of sight.
- $D_H(z) \equiv c/H(z)$ measures directly the expansion rate from the anisotropy in z along the line of sight.
- $D_V(z) = [z(D_M(z)^2 D_H(z))]^{1/3}$ is a combination of the two, giving the isotropic distance.

As these distances are inferred using the calculated sound horizon r_d , the directly constrained quantities are the ratios D_M/r_d , D_H/r_d and D_V/r_d which are plotted in Figure 3.

2.6 Another time inhomogeneity

A cosmological time inhomogeneity (\hat{t}) has been derived from a conformal transformation (L. M. Tomilchik 2014) of the form:

$$\hat{t}_\pm = \frac{t}{(1 \pm H_0 t/2)} \quad (11)$$

where t is the physical (cosmic) time and \pm indicates propagation in the future (+) or past (-), with $\hat{t} = t = 0$ at present. The derivative $d\hat{t}/dt$ is used to calculate a time dilation for past events which induces a redshift \hat{z} :

$$\frac{d\hat{t}}{dt} = \frac{1}{(1 + H_0 t/2)^2} = \frac{\lambda_{obs}}{\lambda_{em}} \equiv (1 + \hat{z}(t)) \quad (12)$$

The SNeIa distance moduli calculated from $\hat{a}(t) \equiv (1 + \hat{z}(t))^{-1}$ in this model are very similar to an EdS universe with $\Omega_m = 1$, i.e. without dark energy. This model will not be considered further.

3 Fitting the data

The following datasets are used to compare the TCDM and Λ CDM models for a flat universe:

- Planck (CMB) (Planck)
- DESI DR2 (BAO: $0.3 < z_{eff} < 2.3$) (DESI2)
- DES-SN5YR (SNeIa: $0.03 < z < 1.0$) (DES Collaboration 2024, hereafter DES5YR)
- Pantheon+ (SNeIa: $0.01 < z < 2.0$) (D. Brout et al. 2022, hereafter Pantheon+)
- SH0ES low- z (SNeIa: $0.001 < z < 0.01$) (A. G. Riess et al. 2022, hereafter SH0ES)

Only the CMB data and the combination of SNeIa data with the SH0ES distance ladder can determine Ω_m and H_0 independently, albeit with high correlation. Their product can be determined with precision, however, due to the negative correlation. Each dataset is usually combined with external ones to remove the degeneracies, which results in a multiplicity of fits for the Λ CDM and other models.

3.1 Fitting individual datasets

In a first step, the TCDM model is compared to the best-fit Λ CDM model published for each dataset. Only dataset combinations with CMB are considered as it imposes tight constraints. An exception is made for the combination Pantheon+ & SH0ES dataset which is not compatible with CMB in a flat Λ CDM model. For CMB, the results of Planck are used, namely the parameters reported in the sixth column of Table 2 therein, which are based on ‘‘TT,TE,EE+lowE+lensing’’, excluding external BAO data. DESI2, however, uses a separate fit to CMB with $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02218 \pm 0.00055$.

Parameter	Planck (CMB)	DESI2+CMB	DES5YR+CMB	Pantheon+&SH0ES
Ω_m	0.3153 ± 0.0073	0.3027 ± 0.0036	0.338 ± 0.015	0.334 ± 0.018
H_0	67.36 ± 0.54	68.17 ± 0.28	...	73.6 ± 1.1
$\Omega_m h^2$	0.1430 ± 0.0011	0.1407 ± 0.0006	(0.1430)	0.1809 ± 0.0045
θ_* (mrad)	10.4110 ± 0.0031	(10.411)	(10.411)	...
b_t	2.11 ± 0.06	2.13 ± 0.07	1.92 ± 0.11	2.22 ± 0.35

Table 1: Parameters of the Λ CDM and TCDM model fits to individual datasets or combinations as indicated. The first two data rows list Ω_m and H_0 ($\text{km s}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}$) of the flat Λ CDM model fit reported in the respective papers. The third and fourth rows list the corresponding density parameter $\Omega_m h^2$ and the acoustic peak θ_* which constrain the flat TCDM model fit. The resulting TCDM exponent b_t is listed in the fifth row. Blanks indicate an absence or incompatibility of data. The external constraints are shown in parentheses.

This value is used when fitting the DESI2+CMB combination with the TCDM model.

The fit results are summarized in Table 1. The first two data rows list the values of Ω_m and H_0 reported by each group for a flat Λ CDM model. The DES5YR analysis leaves H_0 free, even in combination with CMB. This reflects the degeneracy in H_0 and the SNeIa absolute magnitude, both of which contribute a constant offset to the distance modulus. The third row of Table 1 lists the density parameter $\Omega_m h^2$ for each dataset. Only Planck reports a mean value and error for $\Omega_m h^2$ which is used here for DES5YR as well. For DESI2 and Pantheon+ & SH0ES it is calculated from Ω_m and H_0 with an error which takes into account their anti-correlation ($r = -0.98$). The Planck measurement of the acoustic peak θ_* is shown in the fourth row and is used, together with $\Omega_m h^2$, to constrain the TCDM model. The exponent b_t of the TCDM fit and its 68% confidence level (CL) range are listed in the last row.

For all datasets except Pantheon+ & SH0ES, the mean value of b_t is determined mainly by θ_* once $\Omega_m h^2$ is fixed, with the correlation $\Delta\theta_*(\text{mrad}) \sim -0.5\Delta b_t$. For the CMB data, the full acoustic power spectrum is not fit, assuming that using the same parameters as Planck (i.e. $\Omega_m, \Omega_m h^2, \Omega_b h^2$) will reproduce the same secondary peak positions and amplitudes. The 68% CL interval for b_t is estimated by varying the constraints by $\pm 1\sigma$ and adding in quadrature the resulting variations in b_t . For the Pantheon+ & SH0ES dataset, which is fit without the θ_* constraint, the mean and uncertainty in b_t are determined from the χ^2 contours in the $\Omega_m - H_0$ plane subject to the constraint $\Omega_m h^2$.

The TCDM model fit to each dataset yields a

Figure 2: Residuals of SNeIa distance moduli (μ) versus z for the best-fit TCDM model (solid line) after an offset subtraction. The difference of the best-fit Λ CDM (dashed) and w CDM (dotted) models from TCDM are plotted after adjustment for the respective offsets which effectively normalise the models at $z \sim 0.3$.

χ^2 which is comparable or better than the one obtained with the Λ CDM parameters published for the dataset. For DESI2 data, the χ^2 is calculated from $D_V, D_M/D_H$ and D_H data which are plotted in Figure 3. For DES5YR data shown in Figure 2, the χ^2 is calculated after subtracting a constant offset for each model to set the sum of the weighted residuals equal to zero, as done in the publication. The subtraction accounts for leaving H_0 free. For the SH0ES data the χ^2 for μ is calculated using the Cepheid distance, instead of the model, as it is done in Pantheon+. To simplify the model comparison, the full correlation matrices are not used, resulting in a relative χ^2 which is sufficient to compare the two models.

The exponent b_t of the TCDM fit to each dataset varies from 2.12 for the Planck and

DESI2+CMB (with 3.5% uncertainty) to 1.92 for the DES5YR+CMB and 2.22 with 16% uncertainty for the Pantheon+ & SH0ES dataset.

3.2 Fitting all datasets combined

In a second step, the combination of the above datasets, excluding SH0ES data of $z < 0.01$, is fit with flat TCDM and Λ CDM models. In contrast to Section 3.1, the parameters Ω_m , $\Omega_m h^2$, θ_* and H_0 are not fixed to the Λ CDM values published for each dataset but are allowed to vary. The fit uses the tight constraints of Planck by including in the χ^2 the deviations of $\Omega_m h^3 = 0.09633 \pm 0.00030$ (0.3%), $\Omega_m h^2$ and θ_* from their Planck values, assuming Gaussian errors. For the baryon density, the Planck value of $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02237 \pm 0.00015$ is used without any variation. The correlation ma-

trices are again not taken into account.

The best-fit TCDM and Λ CDM models for a flat universe are compared to the data in Figures 2 and 3. The fit parameters and their 68% CL intervals are presented in Table 2.

The residuals of the SNeIa distance moduli (μ) for the best-fit TCDM model are plotted in Figure 2 as a function of redshift. The Pantheon+ data have been grouped into bins of 30 events and the weighted mean μ of each bin is plotted versus the weighted mean z (as is the case for the DES5YR data which also have bins of 30 events). The weighted error is shown for each bin. The χ^2 is calculated for each dataset after adding a constant offset to the distance moduli as described above. For the best-fit TCDM model an offset of 0.061 is added to the μ of DES5YR and an offset of 0.171 is added to Pantheon+.

Figure 3: Ratio of DESI DR2 data to the best-fit TCDM model (solid line) as a function of effective z for: (a) upper left panel: D_V/r_d , (b) lower left panel: D_M/D_H , (c) upper right panel: D_H/r_d . The ratio of the best-fit Λ CDM to TCDM is shown by the dashed line. (d) Lower right panel: Fractional z -drift (Δz) predicted over a ten year period by the best-fit TCDM (solid line) and Λ CDM (dashed line) models as a function of redshift.

Model	Ω_m	H_0 or b_t	θ_* (mrad)	$\Omega_m h^3$	$\Omega_m h^2$
Λ CDM	0.3064 ± 0.0088	68.01 ± 0.65	10.4112 ± 0.0030	0.09637 ± 0.00030	0.1417 ± 0.0013
TCDM	0.3082 ± 0.0088	2.095 ± 0.015	10.4141 ± 0.0062	0.09594 ± 0.00045	0.1416 ± 0.0012

Table 2: The mean value and 68% CL interval for the best-fit TCDM and Λ CDM model parameters.

Λ CDM model shown (dashed line) the offsets are nearly the same as for TCDM. In addition, the best-fit w CDM model published for the DES5YR data with $w_0 = -0.95$ is shown for comparison (dotted line). After subtracting an offset of 0.123, it fits the DES5YR data better than the TCDM model. The apparent normalisation of the three models at $z \sim 0.3$ is a result of applying the offsets. At lower z , the TCDM model falls between Λ CDM and w CDM. The latter diverges at higher z where there is little data.³

BAO data extend measurements to higher redshifts by using the comoving sound horizon r_d as a standard ruler. The DESI2 results shown in Figure 3 are based on the remarkable measurement of ~ 14 million redshifts for four types of tracers in seven redshift intervals extending to $z \sim 3.5$. Following the DESI2 publication, the ratios D_V/r_d , D_M/D_H and D_H/r_d are plotted as a function of the effective z to remove the r_d dependence and they are further normalized by dividing by the best-fit TCDM model values. The best-fit Λ CDM model (dashed line) varies by $\lesssim 0.5\%$ from TCDM and gives a slightly worse fit. The error bars, which do not include model uncertainties, are typically $\pm 1\%$ or greater and do not allow a reliable discrimination between the models.

In Figure 3(c) $D_H(z) \equiv c/H(z)$ measures directly the expansion rate as a function of z . An entirely independent determination of $H(z)$ can be made with real-time z-drift (Δz) measurements (A. Loeb 1998) when they become feasible in the future (Y. Liu et al. 2020):

$$dz/dt_o = H_0(1+z) - H(t_e) \quad (13)$$

where t_e and t_o are respectively the time of emission and of observation of the light in physical time (Weinberg 2008, p.13). Over a period of observation of Δt_o , the change in the redshift of a galaxy, Δz , is given by:

$$\frac{\Delta z}{(1+z)} = \Delta t_o \left[H_0 - \frac{H(z)}{(1+z)} \right] \quad (14)$$

³It is noteworthy that over the range of redshifts plotted in Figure 2, μ spans 11 decades on a logarithmic scale while the residuals are within ± 0.1 on the same scale.

In the TCDM model, the same equation applies after substituting H_0'' and $H(z)''$ for H_0 and $H(z)$.

In Figure 3(d) the predictions of the best-fit TCDM and Λ CDM models are shown for Δz over a period of $\Delta t_o = 10$ years. Future observations by SKA (H. R. Kloeckner et al. 2015) and the European Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) (C. J. A. P. Martins et al. 2024) could measure Δz for $z < 1$ and $z > 2$ respectively. The maximum effect predicted at lower z is $\Delta z \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-10}$ at $z \sim 0.7$, which falls in the SKA range, with a difference between the two models of $\sim 7\%$. For $z > 2$, Δz is negative and the predictions of the two models are very similar.

The parameters of the best-fit flat TCDM and Λ CDM models are presented in Table 2. The TCDM model, with $b_t = 2.095 \pm 0.015$, gives a significantly better fit to the combined data than the best-fit Λ CDM which is in turn a better fit than Planck. Comparing the two best-fit models :

- the density parameter $\Omega_m h^2$ is the same for both which implies good agreement for the expansion of the early Universe,
- the acoustic peak θ_* of the Λ CDM fit agrees well with the Planck measurement while it is 1σ higher for the TCDM fit.

In comparison with Planck, the best-fit Λ CDM model yields lower Ω_m (-1.2σ) and higher H_0 ($+1.2\sigma$) which correspond to a matter density $\Omega_m h^2$ that is 1.2σ lower while the acoustic peak θ_* and the parameter combination $\Omega_m h^3$ are in good agreement.

In the model comparisons of Figures 2 and 3, the difference between flat TCDM and Λ CDM models is predominantly at lower redshift, $z \leq 1$. This is also true for the best-fit w CDM model to DES5YR data shown in Figure 2. In an analysis of DESI2 data combined with CMB and Union3 (SNeIa) (DESI Collaboration 2025b) the difference between the best-fit $w_0 w_a$ CDM and Λ CDM models is significant for $z < 0.4$ as well. A better discrimination between the models should be

possible with higher statistics data at low z which will be available in the near future, in particular:

- the ZTF DR2 cosmology analysis will add $\sim 2.6\text{k}$ SNeIa of $z \leq 0.2$ to the data (M. Rigault et al. 2025),
- the full DESI 5-year data will more than double the DESI2 statistics in three years.

In the longer term, SKA measurements of z -drift could discriminate between dark energy models and TCDM if sufficient precision is achieved.

3.3 Matter density

H_0 , Ω_m and the corresponding matter density $\Omega_m h^2$ of the best-fit flat TCDM and Λ CDM models are plotted in Figure 4. The published values for the Planck, DESI2+CMB and Pantheon+ & SH0ES datasets for a flat universe are also shown. To illustrate the strong anti-correlation between Ω_m and H_0 , their 68% CL interval is shown by a single (long) diagonal error bar whose projections onto the x and y axes indicate the 68% CL intervals for Ω_m and H_0 respectively. The anti-correlation results in a higher precision for the density parameter $\Omega_m h^2$. Contours of constant $\Omega_m h^2$ are shown by dotted lines and the 68% CL for the fit values are indicated by error bars which are orthogonal to the contours.

The four data points in the lower corner which include CMB are in good agreement for the matter density and give a weighted mean value $\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1413 \pm 0.0009$ (0.6% precision) assuming maximal correlation of the datasets. The long diagonal error bars for these four points align along constant $\Omega_m h^3$. The Pantheon+ & SH0ES result in the upper corner, which is not compatible with the CMB acoustic peak, corresponds to a significantly higher matter density of $\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1809 \pm 0.0045$. This value is in 8σ tension with the Planck measurement. At face value, such a high matter density is contrary to hypotheses which attribute the higher H_0 of the SH0ES distance ladder to a local under-density (L. Lombriser 2020).

Regarding the 5σ Hubble tension, which is evident in Figure 4, the power law used for the TCDM model cannot accommodate the higher H_0 measured with the distance ladder to nearby supernovae. To do so, a modification of $b(t)$ in Equation (5) would be required for recent times, in the last $\lesssim 100\text{M}$ years, to increase H_0 without affecting

Figure 4: Mean values of H_0 ($\text{km s}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}$) and Ω_m for a flat universe of the best-fit TCDM and Λ CDM models and three datasets. The projections of the long diagonal error bars onto the x and y axes indicate the 68% CL intervals for Ω_m and H_0 respectively. The matter density $\Omega_m h^2$ for each datum can be read using the scale defined by the contours of constant $\Omega_m h^2$ (dotted lines). Its 68% CL is indicated by an error bar which is orthogonal to the contours.

the CMB and BAO angles significantly. It would, however, raise another Coincidence Problem.

4 Conclusions

The hypothesis of a cosmological time coordinate t' which varies non-uniformly with respect to the physical (cosmic) time coordinate t describes well the expansion of the Universe without requiring dark energy. The $\Delta t'$ and Δt time scales, which are identical initially, evolve with an ansatz power law whose exponent is the only free parameter. This time-inhomogeneity hypothesis with cold dark matter (TCDM model) fits recent cosmological datasets from CMB, BAO and distant SNeIa measurements comparably or better than the Λ CDM fit to each one. Fitting all datasets combined, the flat TCDM model with the exponent $b_t = 2.095 \pm 0.015$ and the matter density $\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1416 \pm 0.0012$ describes the data well, making dark energy superfluous. It is a significantly better fit than the best-fit flat Λ CDM model which yields $H_0 = 68.01 \pm 0.65 \text{ km s}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ and the same $\Omega_m h^2$ (i.e. $\Omega_m = 0.3064 \pm 0.0088$ with

$\sim 69\%$ dark energy).

In the near future, higher statistics BAO and SNeIa data for $z \leq 0.5$ could discriminate between the two models as well as the w CDM and w_0w_a CDM alternatives for dark energy. In the longer term, real-time z -drift measurements by SKA around $z \sim 0.7$ could be decisive, if sufficient precision is achieved.

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